

Modeling of a device for conducting experiments under low reactor neutron fluence rate conditions

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Abstract

The study focuses on modeling a device designed for conducting experiments under low reactor neutron fluence rate conditions. The relevance of the work is driven by the challenges of accurately measuring low reactor neutron fluence rates, which are critical for the safety and efficiency of nuclear reactors and for conducting research in various scientific fields. To create a directed neutron flux, a horizontal collimation channel of the Prizm-AN irradiation device with a radioisotope capsule neutron source of the internal bounded neutron (IBN) type is being investigated. The paper presents the results of particle transport modeling using the PHITS and SOURCES-4C codes, which allowed for the evaluation of the generated neutron fluence rate parameters and the effective dose rate of radiation. The obtained results confirm the functionality of the proposed device and its compliance with radiation safety requirements, making it suitable for conducting experiments similar to those performed on reactor installations.

Keywords

fluence rate, neutron detector, nuclear reactor, PHITS modeling, Pu-Be source, radiation safety

Introduction

Measuring neutron fluence rate is critically important for ensuring the safety and efficient operation of nuclear reactors, including research reactor installations and at low power levels. However, detecting low levels of neutron fluence rate poses significant challenges. Existing methods face considerable difficulties, such as insufficient sensitivity of installed detectors, for example, scintillation detectors with low scintillator efficiency, and the inability to use certain types of detectors, such as activation detectors, for extended periods (Moslehi et al. 2022; Teimoory et al. 2024). This complicates reactor optimization, reliable experimentation in fields like nuclear medicine and materials science, and limits the possibilities for fundamental physical research.

Numerous experiments on installations similar to the miniature neutron source reactor in Isfahan confirm the existence of this problem when conducting irradiation experiments outside the reactor core and at low neutron fluence rates (Mokhtari et al. 2017, 2023; Dastjerdi et al. 2019; Mokhtari and Choopan Dastjerdi 2023).

To address these issues, this study focuses on modeling the Prizm-AN irradiation device, which generates a directed neutron flux using a Pu-Be neutron source. The materials and the geometry of the device are modeled in order to calculate the neutron and gamma fluence rate distributions inside and outside the polyethylene prism. The device is designed to simulate low reactor neutron fluence rate conditions, enabling experiments without requiring direct access to a nuclear reactor, which is particularly relevant for regions with limited reactor availability.

The modeling was conducted using the verified PHITS and SOURCES-4C codes to ensure radiation safety assessment. The calculated data obtained from the modeling will confirm the results of experiments related to neutron detector calibration.

Materials and methods

Neutron source IBN-10

Neutron sources come in several types and produce neutrons with various energy spectra. The neutron flux in sealed sources is accompanied mainly by gamma radiation. Therefore, due to the high radiation hazard, neutron sources must be placed in a suitable capsule.

The Pu-Be neutron source produces fast neutrons through the (α , n) reaction. The main characteristics of the internal bounded neutron (IBN) type source IBN-10 are provided in Table 1 according to the technical passport.

Table 1. Technical characteristics of the IBN-10 neutron source

Name of characteristic	Value
Fast neutron flux from the source in a solid angle of 4π	10^7 s^{-1}
External diameter	35 mm
External height	45 mm
Internal diameter	27 mm
Internal height	27 mm

The IBN-10 neutron source has a cylindrical shape and consists of an intermetallic mixture of PuO_2+Be and an external capsule made of 12Cr18Ni10Ti steel; its geometry is shown in Fig. 1. The calculation model uses a simplified geometry with equivalent dimensions to maintain the same volume of the external capsule.

12Cr18Ni10Ti steel with a density of 7.9 g/cm^3 has the following composition: C – 0.12 wt.%, Si – 0.80 wt.%, Mn – 2.00 wt.%, Cr – 19.00 wt.%, Ni – 11.00 wt.%, Ti – 0.80 wt.%, S – 0.02 wt.%, P – 0.04 wt.%, Fe – 66.22 wt.% (GOST 5632 2015).

The main reason for choosing PuO_2 as a neutron source is its availability in our laboratory, as well as its wide-

Figure 1. Geometry of IBN-10 neutron source (1 – radioisotope source PuO_2+Be ; 2 – external capsule made of 12Cr18Ni10Ti steel). **A)** Geometry of the calculation model; **B)** real geometry of IBN-1–IBN-12 sources (Isotope JSC 2013).

spread production in Russia, in contrast to conventional Pu-Be sources.

Sealed neutron sources have a continuous spectrum. The emission neutron spectrum is another important characteristic that must be considered when building the calculation model. The manufacturer specifies in the technical documentation the fast neutron flux from the source in a solid angle of 4π , s^{-1} (see Table 1). The required emission spectrum is reconstructed based on the manufacturer's experimental data on the flux using the SOURCES-4C code.

SOURCES-4C is a program that can determine the intensity of neutron radiation and spectra of (α , n) reactions, spontaneous fission, and delayed neutrons. The code can calculate the radiation intensity of the source used in the (α , n) reaction and the neutron spectra (Wilson et al. 2009). The homogeneous mixture model is chosen in SOURCES-4C due to the actual homogeneity of the real source's composition.

The model allows for the calculation of α -particle transport, neutron yield, and spectrum for a homogeneous mixture of α -emitters and light elements. Here, materials subject to α -decay and spontaneous fission are closely mixed with the target material with low Z. Three types of neutrons are considered: spontaneous fission neutrons, delayed neutrons, and neutrons emitted as a result of (α , n) reactions. The model assumes that the target size is much smaller than the range of α -particles, so all α -particles stop within the mixture of target nuclei and α -emitters. The neutron spectra of the (α , n) reaction are determined under the assumption of isotropic angular distribution of neutrons in the center of mass system (Wilson et al. 2009).

The considered neutron energy range is from 0 to 12 MeV and is divided into 52 equivalent monoenergetic groups. The neutron spectrum is shown in Fig. 2 along

Figure 2. Neutron spectrum of IBN-10 and ISO 8529-1 reference spectrum.

with the reference spectrum recommended by the IAEA (ISO 8529-1 2021).

Calculation model of Prizm-AN irradiation device

Polyethylene with a density of 0.93 g/cm^3 (Detwiler et al. 2021) is used. Due to the moderating and, consequently, reflecting properties of polyethylene, neutrons can be thermalized and directed in a specific direction. In this regard,

Figure 3. Geometric model of the Prizm-AN device with the IBN-10 source.

a polyethylene prism with a collimation channel located along the lateral axis is modeled. The source is placed at the maximum depth of the channel. Prizm-AN with the IBN-10 source is shown in Fig. 3. For further modeling, the zero-point indicated on the diagram is used, and axes are drawn through it to calculate the neutron fluence rate distribution and other parameters. In further work to increase the fluence rate level to values characteristic of calibration, 18 IBN-10 capsules are installed according to a $3 \times 3 \times 2$ scheme. The detectors can then be calibrated by exposing them to a directed neutron beam at known fluence rates and comparing the responses with simulated values.

Calculation model of Prizm-AN for the PHITS code

PHITS v 2.88 (Particle and Heavy Ion Transport code System) is a general-purpose code for simulating particle transport using the Monte Carlo method (Sato et al. 2015).

The PHITS code can simulate the transport of almost all particles over a wide energy range, as it can handle neutron transport from thermal energies up to 200 GeV. Among the wide energy range for neutron transport using the PHITS code, we will focus only on neutrons with energies below 20 MeV, as the Pu-Be source in our calculation experiment produces neutrons with a maximum energy of 11 MeV, as seen in Fig. 2. This is important to note because PHITS divides energy into ranges and uses a special data library for each range, which affects the reliability of the simulation results obtained by PHITS. For neutrons with energies below 20 MeV, PHITS uses a nuclear data library, while for neutrons with energies above 20 MeV, it uses parameterization (PHITS 2016).

The PHITS input data used in this work consist of several sections described below.

The “Parameters” section mainly affects the statistical error of the calculations. The number of particles per batch and the number of batches when multiplied give the number of histories. For high-precision calculations, the number of histories should be 10^9 or more, so the number of particles per batch is set to 10^7 , and the number of batches is set to 100. Also, in this section, the parameter “ $\text{igamma} = 1$ ” is set to enable the gamma decay option for residual nuclei formed as a result of neutron reactions.

In the “Source” section, an isotropic source is set at the end of the prism channel, as shown in Fig. 3; the materials and geometric dimensions are given in Table 1. In this section, only the internal dimensions of the source are used, as only the internal part contains radioactive material. In this work, two separate models were implemented for obtaining correct calculations – one with a neutron source and one with a gamma radiation source. These models use the same input data, except for the “Source” section.

In the model with a neutron source, the reconstructed neutron emission yield from SOURCES is used as the normalization coefficient, so all calculated values are expressed in absolute units. The neutron spectrum from the source is set according to the data presented in Fig. 2.

In the model with gamma radiation sources, each radioisotope is set in the same volume but as a separate source with its own activity. The gamma radiation spectra from these sources are automatically set according to the data stored in PHITS. Since the activity is entered in Bq, all calculated values are expressed in absolute units.

The geometry of the models was built using several sections. First, the materials were defined using the “Material” section: the intermetallic mixture of PuO_2 and Be, steel 12Cr18Ni10Ti, polyethylene, and air. Only the atomic fractions of the elements composing the material can be used as input data, so, if necessary, their calculation was performed using mass fractions and molar masses of the natural element.

Second, four rectangular solid macro-bodies were created in the “Surface” section: the external capsule of the source, the prism, the channel, and the space around the prism.

Finally, in section “Cell”, the prism macrobody was subtracted from the space macrobody, the channel macrobody from the prism macrobody, and the outer source capsule from the channel macrobody. As a result, it was possible to assign appropriate materials with appropriate densities: $\text{PuO}_2 + \text{Be}$ – for the radioisotope source, steel – for the outer source capsule, C_2H_4 – for the prism, and air – for the channel and the space around the prism.

The dimensions are set on a 1:1 scale to those specified in Table 1 and Fig. 3, as the program uses centimeters as the standard unit of measurement. The geometric image of the prism obtained using the “T-3dshow” section is shown in Fig. 4 and confirms the accuracy of the geometric modeling.

Results and discussion

IBN-10 source in air

Figure 4. Calculation model of Prizm-AN (1 – collimation channel; 2 – polyethylene prism).

To evaluate the correctness of the model, the prism material is set as air instead of polyethylene, so the IBN-10 source is in the air, while maintaining the same geometric model for further comparison.

The neutron fluence rate distributions along the Y-axis for neutrons with different energies are shown in Fig. 5A, with the graphs obtained using the “T-track” section in the model with a neutron source. The energy ranges are defined as follows: thermal neutrons – from 0 to 0.5 eV, resonance neutrons – from 0.5 eV to 100 keV, fast neutrons – from 100 keV to 20 MeV. Due to the absence of a moderator in this case, the thermal neutron fluence rate is close to zero.

The gamma radiation fluence rate distribution along the Y-axis is shown in Fig. 5B and obtained using the “T-track” section. In the model with a neutron source, gamma radiation arises from the decay of residual nuclei formed as a result of neutron reactions. In the model with a gamma radiation source, gamma radiation arises from the decay of radionuclides in the IBN-10 source.

A

B

Figure 5. Fluence rate distribution along the Y-axis. **A)** Neutron radiation; **B)** gamma radiation.

In the study by Peleshko et al. (2019), an IBN-25 source with a neutron radiation intensity of 10^7 s^{-1} was used. For the IBN-25 source, the neutron fluence rate at a distance of 1 m is estimated at $98.6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for neutrons with $E > 0.4 \text{ eV}$. In this case, the deviation of the calculated neutron fluence rate from the reference result is 14.9%, mainly due to the difference in the geometry – IBN-25 source has a different external height, which equals 39 mm (Isotope JSC 2013). When using the IBN-25 source in the model, the result is estimated at $92.6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, so the deviation decreases to 6%. The results are also consistent with the studies by Nguyen et al. (2024) and Vega-Carrillo et al. (2002).

Since the neutron fluence rate values obtained are consistent with the results of other studies, it is safe to say that the model is correct.

IBN-10 source in polyethylene prism

Due to the presence of a moderator, a thermal neutron fluence rate is formed. Thanks to the reflecting properties of the moderator, some neutrons are directed into the channel, thereby increasing the neutron fluence rate. However, in all other directions, including the negative Y-axis, the neutron fluence rate is significantly reduced due to the thick polyethylene layer, which slows down and captures neutrons. The gamma radiation fluence rate increases due to radiative neutron capture. The distributions of neutron and gamma radiation fluence rates along the Y-axis in the presence of the polyethylene prism are shown in Fig. 6; Fig. 7 shows the neutron fluence rate distribution on the YZ plane.

In the “T-track” section, the effective dose rate can be evaluated using the “Multiplier” section, where the fluence-to-dose conversion coefficients in $\text{pSv} \cdot \text{cm}^2$ are set according to the tables (ICRP 2010) for neutrons and gamma radiation, respectively. The graph of the effective dose rate distribution in $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ has the same shape as the particle fluence rate distribution.

The limit for occupational exposure is 20 mSv in a year, averaged over defined periods of 5 years, with no

Figure 6. Fluence rate distribution along the Y-axis. **A)** Neutron radiation; **B)** gamma radiation.

Figure 7. Neutron fluence rate distribution on the YZ plane. **A)** Thermal neutrons; **B)** resonance neutrons; **C)** fast neutrons; **D)** total neutron radiation.

single year exceeding 50 mSv (ICRP 2007). At the limit of 20 mSv, the permissible operating time at various points along the Y-axis from the device is presented in

Table 2, along with the particle fluence rate and effective dose rate values at these points.

While concrete is the material most commonly employed in reactor channel designs due to its struc-

Table 2. Radiation characteristics at various points along the Y-axis

Point	Fluence rate, $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$		Effective dose rate, $\mu\text{Sv/h}$			Permissible operating time, h
	Neutrons	Photons	Neutrons	Photons	Total	
Source center	$1.08 \cdot 10^6$	$2.72 \cdot 10^8$	$7.91 \cdot 10^5$	$1.93 \cdot 10^5$	$9.84 \cdot 10^5$	0.02
Source surface	$2.65 \cdot 10^5$	$8.69 \cdot 10^5$	$1.84 \cdot 10^5$	$2.00 \cdot 10^3$	$1.86 \cdot 10^5$	0.11
Prism surface	$1.59 \cdot 10^3$	$3.11 \cdot 10^3$	$3.27 \cdot 10^2$	$1.09 \cdot 10^1$	$3.38 \cdot 10^2$	59.25
10 cm from the prism	$7.15 \cdot 10^2$	$2.97 \cdot 10^3$	$2.08 \cdot 10^2$	6.31	$2.15 \cdot 10^2$	93.19
20 cm from the prism	$4.04 \cdot 10^2$	$1.35 \cdot 10^3$	$1.46 \cdot 10^2$	5.80	$1.51 \cdot 10^2$	132.02
40 cm from the prism	$2.06 \cdot 10^2$	$5.99 \cdot 10^2$	$8.38 \cdot 10^1$	1.85	$8.56 \cdot 10^1$	233.63
50 cm from the prism	$1.45 \cdot 10^2$	$3.32 \cdot 10^2$	$6.00 \cdot 10^1$	1.40	$6.14 \cdot 10^1$	325.84
80 cm from the prism	$8.33 \cdot 10^1$	$2.53 \cdot 10^2$	$3.58 \cdot 10^1$	$6.89 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.65 \cdot 10^1$	547.98
100 cm from the prism	$6.09 \cdot 10^1$	$2.43 \cdot 10^2$	$2.50 \cdot 10^1$	$4.56 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.55 \cdot 10^1$	785.76

Figure 8. Comparison of fluence rate distributions in concrete and polyethylene prisms. **A)** Neutron radiation; **B)** gamma radiation.

tural and shielding properties, its high density, which equals 2.3 g/cm^3 for regular concrete (Detwiler et al. 2021), would compromise the portability of the proposed device. In contrast, polyethylene offers distinct advantages for this application. Its higher hydrogen content relative to density enables efficient neutron thermalization and reflection, achieving a neutron fluence rate in the collimation channel comparable to that of concrete (Fig. 8A).

Furthermore, polyethylene significantly reduces fluence rates in unintended directions, enhancing directional control of the neutron beam. However, the increased radiative neutron capture in polyethylene elevates the gamma fluence rate (Fig. 8B). For experimental setups prioritizing portability and neutron beam precision – particularly in field applications or facilities without reactor access – polyethylene presents a viable alternative to conventional concrete channels.

Assembly of IBN-10 capsules in Prism-AN

The distributions of neutron and gamma radiation fluence rates along the Y-axis for the model with 18 IBN-10 sources in the polyethylene prism are shown in Fig. 9;

Fig. 10 shows the neutron fluence rate distribution on the YZ plane. The radiation characteristics at various points along the Y-axis are presented in Table 3.

The neutron fluence rate along the channel length varies from 10^4 to $10^5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ depending on the distance from the sources (Fig. 9). For Prism-AN equipped with one capsule, the neutron fluence rate in the channel and at further distances ranges from 10^2 to $10^4 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 6).

Various detectors can be used on the nuclear reactor, corresponding to power requirements, with fission chambers being the most commonly employed. These detectors use fissile materials to convert thermal neutrons into detectable ions (Chabod et al. 2006; Jammes et al. 2011; He et al. 2017). The use of our device allows for preliminary experiments and calibration of fission chambers without the need for a neutron source reactor, as their response is completely linear in the neutron fluence rate range from 10^2 to $10^5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Teimoory et al. 2024) and can be used with high confidence for experiments with relatively low neutron fluence rate (Mokhtari et al. 2017; Dastjerdi et al. 2019; Moslehi et al. 2022; Mokhtari and Choopan Dastjerdi 2023; Mokhtari et al. 2023).

Figure 9. Fluence rate distribution along the Y-axis. **A)** Neutron radiation; **B)** gamma radiation.

Figure 10. Neutron fluence rate distribution on the YZ plane. **A)** Thermal neutrons; **B)** resonance neutrons; **C)** fast neutrons; **D)** total neutron radiation.

The neutron fluence rate can be fine-tuned by adjusting the number of IBN-10 capsules or incorporating movable polyethylene reflectors. During long-term use, periodic recalibration is carried out taking into account the decrease in source activity.

The permissible operating time is acceptable (Tables 2, 3) and can be increased by moving away from the path of the directed neutron beam and using a cover on the collimation channel.

The proposed Prizm-AN device could potentially support nuclear reactor maintenance and fuel verification by

Table 3. Radiation characteristics at various points along the Y-axis

Point	Fluence rate, cm ² s ⁻¹		Effective dose rate, μSv/h			Permissible operating time, h
	Neutrons	Photons	Neutrons	Photons	Total	
Source center	2.49·10 ⁶	2.00·10 ⁸	1.43·10 ⁶	1.55·10 ³	1.59·10 ⁶	0.01
Source surface	2.07·10 ⁶	3.17·10 ⁶	1.09·10 ⁶	1.69·10 ⁴	1.10·10 ⁶	0.02
Prism surface	2.90·10 ⁴	3.26·10 ⁴	6.36·10 ³	1.94·10 ²	6.55·10 ³	3.05
10 cm from the prism	1.18·10 ⁴	2.25·10 ⁴	3.98·10 ³	1.19·10 ²	4.10·10 ³	4.88
20 cm from the prism	5.56·10 ³	9.55·10 ³	2.46·10 ³	6.07·10 ¹	2.52·10 ³	7.95
40 cm from the prism	2.77·10 ³	1.10·10 ⁴	9.98·10 ²	3.66·10 ¹	1.03·10 ³	19.34
50 cm from the prism	2.58·10 ³	6.38·10 ³	1.41·10 ³	1.93·10 ¹	1.43·10 ³	14.02
80 cm from the prism	1.66·10 ³	4.09·10 ³	1.05·10 ³	8.19	1.06·10 ³	18.89
100 cm from the prism	1.12·10 ³	5.26·10 ³	5.91·10 ²	1.83·10 ¹	6.09·10 ²	32.84

enabling detector calibration and material testing without reactor access. In nuclear medicine, it could aid in boron neutron capture therapy research, while its portability and safety could make it suitable for space radiation studies, such as testing shielding materials or electronics. By offering a cost-effective, reactor-free alternative, the model bridges gaps in neutron-based experimentation across multiple fields.

Conclusions

Measuring neutron fluence rate, especially at low levels characteristic of certain reactor operating modes or during experiments, is crucial for ensuring safety, optimizing reactor performance, and obtaining reliable experimental results in various scientific fields. This paper presents a comprehensive study on the calibration of neutron detectors, particularly focusing on an experimental device that includes an IBN-10 neutron source placed in a polyethylene prism. The obtained results demonstrate the possibility of using a Pu-Be neutron source to create a directed neutron flux by employing a polyethylene prism with an irradiation channel.

The experimental results confirm that the simulated device operates reliably in terms of particle fluence rate distribution. When using 18 IBN-10 sources, the neutron and gamma radiation fluence rates at a distance of 1 m from the prism are $1.12 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $5.26 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, with the total effective dose rate being $6.09 \cdot 10^2$

μSv/h. The analysis of effective dose rates ensures compliance with occupational exposure limits, suggesting that adequate protective measures can significantly extend the permissible operating time.

The PHITS simulation confirms that the required neutron fluence rate for the operation of a neutron detector can be achieved using this device. The study validates the suitability of the simulated device for the task of calibrating fission chambers designed to operate under low reactor neutron fluence rate conditions. The deployment of multiple IBN-10 sources significantly increases the neutron fluence rate, thereby enhancing the efficiency of detector calibration while adhering to radiation safety protocols. Furthermore, this device will enable a series of experiments similar to those conducted in reactors, as it can generate neutron fluence rates ranging from 10^2 to $10^5 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$.

In conclusion, this research lays the foundation for future advancements in neutron detection and underscores the critical role of empirical testing in improving neutron detection techniques under nuclear reactor conditions.

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- Supplementary material 1**
Original data sheets
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 Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.11.149291.suppl1>